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In this article, such a concept as: "automation of the production process" was considered. The article identified its main principles, advantages and disadvantages. So, based on the foregoing, we can conclude that the growth of scientific progress opens up great opportunities for the development of production, the improvement of technology and equipment, which is the solution to many problems in the production process. And it is the automation of production that makes it possible to reduce the time of production, improve its quality, and also increase the competitiveness of the enterprise, which will positively affect the sales market of goods.

In the article, an example "**Technical and information support of intelligent power supply systems**" reviewed the automation of technological processes

Keywords: innovative technologies, development of robotic mechanisms, automatic control system, cyberization.

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Introduction

Recently, the automation of technological processes has become an actively developing area of scientific ideas. This is due, first of all, to the improvement of innovative technologies, and software in various branches of production and industry, and the use of technologies that make it easier for a person to work. The study of materials of scientific works makes it possible to identify such areas of process automation as:

- the possibility of using electronics, electronic equipment for control and monitoring, sensors, equipment with automation of work, and the development of robotic mechanisms. The innovative development of technology today presupposes the highest degree of automation and cyberization.

So, N.F. Voinovai noted that improving quality through the introduction of process automation will increase the efficiency of modern production, increase productivity, improve product quality, and minimize waste in production [1].

Automation is recognized as the direction of scientific and technological progress, which finds expression in the use of self-regulating technical means, methods, and control systems that completely free a person from participation in production processes or information.

The main goal of automation of technological processes:

- increasing the efficiency and perfection of the production process;
- Increasing and ensuring the safety of the production process.

The goals are achieved by solving a number of tasks:

- improvement of the quality of regulation;
- increase in equipment readiness factor;
- improvement of labor ergonomics of the production process;

The solution of the tasks is carried out with the help of:

- introduction of modern methods of automation;

- introduction of modern means of automation.

The great importance of automation of technological processes lies in the fact that within the framework of one production process it is possible to organize a production management system and an enterprise management system. The introduction of automation requires the utmost clarity in the work of all parts of the enterprise production process system.

Automation of the production process, as a rule, is created using an automated process control system (APCS) [4]. The process control system is a comprehensive solution that provides automation of the main production operations.

The process control system is a centralized control system for the production process in the form of control panels, means of processing or storing information during the process or production. Information communication between subsystems is established by industrial networks.

For the development of automated production, the following principles must be observed:

- the principle of completeness, i.e. the desire to perform operations within the automated process system;

- the principle of low-operational technology, i.e. the number of intermediate operations should be kept to a minimum;

- the principle of low-human technology, i.e. ensuring automatic work throughout the process;

- the principle of optimality, i.e. production facilities and services are subordinated to a single optimal solution. [5].

Serial and small-scale production is characterized by the creation of automated systems from universal and aggregate equipment with interoperational tanks, which has the possibility of readjustment.

Automation in large-scale production is determined by the creation of systems from aggregate and universal equipment, united by a connection between them. According to the types of equipment layout, there are:

- single-flow automated production;
- multithreaded automated production;
- production of parallel aggregation.

The development of automated systems for the production process should be carried out in accordance with the following requirements:

- open system architecture;
- interaction between different levels of the system;
- phased introduction of the system into operation and its development.

The introduction of production automation provides:

- improving the quality of products;
- positive dynamics of labor productivity growth;
- increase of efficiency of activity;
- increase in the level of safety [6].

Results obtained and their discussion

An example "Technical and information support of intelligent power supply systems" reviewed the automation of technological processes.

A positive criterion from the introduction of an automated system is also an increase in profits, a decrease in defects in production; reducing the cost of products, improving the quality of products and control. There are also problematic aspects of production automation, among which we can single out the complication of the production system, retraining of personnel, as well as rising unemployment.

Visualization software is used to solve the following tasks:

1. Reproduction of data in graphical form (mnemonics);
2. Indication of a violation of the normal operation of the equipment;

3. Data archiving of information on the course of the technological process;

4. Providing accessible control by the operator over control objects;

5. Access control and recording of operations performed by the dispatcher;

6. Automated generation of reporting protocols for a certain period of time.

One of the most significant problems associated with factory automation is "technological unemployment," which is the loss of jobs caused by technological change. This problem causes negative views on the introduction of automation. Also, a significant problem is the lack of qualified personnel, since personnel working under the old program do not know innovative work standards. Nevertheless, I would like to note that there are much more positive sides than negative ones, and therefore, most enterprises tend to switch to automated labor. In this connection, in order to eliminate the shortcomings of the automated system, it is necessary to create an effective production control system.

"A software package for process visualization (SCADA) is installed at the operator's station. Most visualization packages work under the Windows operating systems" [7].

The process screens displayed on the workstation of the operational personnel of the service contain mnemonic frames that provide access to the terminals and emergency recorders (if any). Examples of mnemonic diagrams are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Example of mnemonic diagrams.

In the process of analyzing oscillograms on the workstation, it is possible to:

- receiving already pre-processed information from the System Server in the form of a single, emergency process;
- full access to archival information on the server;
- selection of emergency information by templates;
- combining in one accident up to 1000 oscillograms of emergency processes;
- display on the oscillogram of the sequence of operation of protections, blinkers, switching equipment and other discrete signals that take place in the general archive of the APCS;
- joint display of graphs of analog and discrete values, including those from different connections, on one oscillogram;

- automatic splitting into frames according to user-defined criteria (one frame contains information from physically related values, for example, 3 phases of currents and 3 phases of voltages by connections);

- "scroll" mode of oscillograms;

- the presence of an overview frame that allows for express analysis of the entire emergency process and quickly navigate through the accident;

- scaling along the X, Y axes of graphs;

- highlighting the color of curves and marking points;

- determining the amplitude and effective values of currents and voltages, as well as measuring time intervals;

- construction of vector diagrams;

- spectral analysis;

- filtering U, I "according to the first harmonic";

- saving the received information in a local archive on the workstation of the RPA and ACS service for long-term storage or exchange of information between the PS services;
- documenting the received information;

- organizing the transfer of the received information to the upper level.

Examples of mnemonic diagrams of the CRA oscillogram processing subsystem are shown in the figures 2.

Figure 2. Examples of mnemonic diagrams of the CRA oscillogram.

Figure 3 shows a block diagram of the proposed testing methodology.

Figure 3. Technological scheme of the testing algorithm.

In the process of designing the device, it is necessary to define a detailed testing plan. The testing plan contains requirements based on the specification of the tested device, a list of the necessary equipment for the test environment, a description of all planned tests and expected testing results. As input data in each phase, we use the testing plan, as an output from each stage, we receive a report on the successfully completed testing results and the one where we have to repeat the tests or report on the error. If some requirements have not passed the testing, it is important to use a system in the form of a problem/question - a tracking system through which the test engineer reports that the error was found".

Depending on whether testing is carried out, the error report is directed to the study or development group.

When the corresponding group corrects the error, it reports that the error has been corrected, then the test engineer repeats the stage at which he discovered the error and because of which the tests were stopped.

The first phase consists in studying the correctness of the hardware device. Inspection of the demonstration assembly scheme, connections in it, assembled electronic components, detection, verification and correction of errors that may have occurred during manufacture.

The assembled demonstration assembly schemes are tested for the presence of electrical connections and infinite resistance in various nodes.

The next stage is assembly (soldering), where optical tests and X-ray radiation are used to check whether the right components are in the right place, and whether they are correctly oriented or there are bad solders, short circuits, etc.

The second phase is testing the software of the device. After the equipment testing report is marked positive, we proceed to check the device's performance. The complexity of this phase depends on the design of the device.

Functionality testing is defined as an activity that is carried out in order to evaluate the quality of the equipment and software of the system, for their improvement, through the detection of defects and errors. The testing plan at this stage contains the requirements prepared in accordance with the specifications of the device, a description of the test environment that will simulate a realistic working environment of the IU, detailed instructions for the testing process, which provide for all the functions supported by the IU and the expected test result. Depending on the purpose of the device, the acceptable deviation from the test result will be determined.

Conclusion

Automatic control system for technological processes means should ensure the implementation of the control and control system of the substation, which solves the task of control, control, measurements and

diagnostics with the transfer of information to the network control center.

At the same time, Automatic control system for technological processes substations will perform the functions of traditional telemechanics devices.

The software and technical means included in the Automatic control system for technological processes 220/110/10 kV must be serial, unified, with a service life of at least 12 years (taking into account the timely maintenance of individual components and the system as a whole).

The average service life of terminals for protection and automation should be no less than 20 years.

The basic technological and general system functions of Automatic control system for technological processes (ACS TP) are investigated, as well as related means and systems of control and control of the substation.

Technological functions include:

- control of the current mode and state of the main circuit of the substation;
- automated control of switching devices 220/110/10 kV;
- technological emergency and warning signaling in ACS TP;
- registration of emergency situations in ACS TP;
- control (monitoring) of the electrical equipment status ;
- technical accounting of electricity. Balance calculations;
- control quality of electricity;
- determination of the location of damage on VL 220 and VL 110 kV;

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